

Pharmaceutical Study of *Shatavari Kalpa*

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ABSTRACT :

Background : *Shatavari Kalpa* is unique formulation indicated as female reproductive tonic. *Shatavari* has important role to maintain *Swasthya* (Health) of female as having actions of *Rasayan* and *Balya*. It offers a rich , comprehensive outlook to a healthy life and occupied a prime position in practise. Due to increasing demand of this formulation there is need to work on pharmaceutical aspect of this formulation in each and every aspect. Hence, an attempt was done for conducting pharmaceutical study of *Shatavari Kalpa*.

Aim: To study the pharmaceutical procedure of *Shatavari Kalpa*.

Material and Method: Two batches of *Shatavari Kalpa* were prepared *Samguna Sharkara* and *Dwigun Sharkara*. and the average required for preparation of *Shatavari Kalpa* was one day. A constant heat of 80 to 95 °C was maintained throughout the procedure.

Result and Conclusion: The detailed pharmaceutical study of *Shatavari Kalpa* in stepwise description and documentation provide detail scientific data for future researcher.

Keywords: *Shatavari, Shatavari Paka, Khanda Kalpana, Balya, Rasayan.*

INTRODUCTION :

Bhaishjyakalpana is a pharmaceutical branch of Ayurveda has contributed various innovative dosage forms. The medicinal formulations are prepared by potentiating properties of drugs.

There are many pharmaceutical methods developed for various medicines preparation to compete with need of all time availability, easy dispensing, and efficacy. In the same sequence, Acharya has mentioned different formulations, such as *Kwath*, *Churna*, *Vati*, and *Avalehas* semi-solid medicated formulations, with similar herbal ingredients but vary in proportion of ingredients, efficacy, dose, and palatability, and so on. [1]

Conversion of dosage form is more suitable for modern era with additional benefits of palatability.

Many formulations of *Shatavari* are mentioned in classical text. *Shatavari Kalpa* is an herbal formulation, Preparation of granules is one of the modified form of *Ghana* and *Khanda Kalpana*. *Khanda* is a granule preparation and its assimilation starts from the buccal cavity. [2]

Shatavari Kalpa is one of the well-known formulation for its beneficial properties like *Stanyajanan*, *Balya*, *Brihan*, *Rasayan*, *Vajikaran*, *Amlapittahar* etc. [3] Hence, this study was planned for the preparation and analysis of *Shatavari* granules.

AIM :

To study the pharmaceutical procedure of *Shatavari Kalpa*.

OBJECTIVES :

1. To study the procedure of *Shatavari Paka Nirman*.
2. To highlight the concept of *Khanda Kalpana*.

REFERANCE :

There is no basic reference of *Shatavari Kalpa Nirman* available in classical textbook.

DRUG REVIEW: ^[4]

- ❖ *Dravya* – *Shatavari*
- ❖ **Latin name** – *Asparagus recemosus*.
- ❖ **Family** – Liliaceae
- ❖ **Synonyms** – *Shatamuli, Shatavirya, Atirasa, Bahusuta, Narayani, Bhiru*
- ❖ **Rasa** – *Madhur, Tikta*
- ❖ **Guna** – *Snigdha, Guru*
- ❖ **Virya** - *Shita*
- ❖ **Vipaka** - *Madhur*
- ❖ **Prayojyang** – *Kanda*
- ❖ **Chemical constituents** – Saponin, Flavonide, Glycoside
- ❖ **Karma** – *Balya, Rasayan, Medhya, Hrudya, Stanyajanan, Vatapittaraktahar*

MATERIAL AND METHADODOLOGY :

General method of preparation emphasized for *Khanda Paka* is followed in the preparation of *Shatavari* granules. ^[5]

The raw materials required for preparation *Shatavari Kalpa* were collected from authenticated source.

INGREDIENTS:**Table no 1 showing ingredients of Shatavari Kalpa**

Sr. no.	Ingredients	Quantity taken
1	<i>Shatavari (Mula)</i>	500 gm
2	<i>Khanda Sharkara</i>	1.5 kg
3	<i>Prakshep Dravya</i> – 1) <i>Sariva</i>	15 gm
4	2) <i>Ela</i>	10 gm
5	Water	9 litres

EQUIPMENTS :

- ✓ Stainless steel vessel
- ✓ Spatula
- ✓ Measuring jar
- ✓ Muslin cloth
- ✓ Weighing machine
- ✓ Gas Stove

Preparation of *Shatavari Kalpa* consist of following steps :

A. Preparation of *Shatavari Kwath* (Decoction).

B. Preparation of *Shatavari Kalpa* by *Samaguna Sharkara* (Batch A) and *Dwiguna Sharkara* (Batch B).

A. Preparation of *Shatavari Kwath* :

1. 500 gm of *Shatavari* roots were taken in vessel and soaked in eight parts of water (4 liter) overnight.
2. On next day 1 liter water was absorbed by *Shatavari* roots.
3. *Shatavari Nal* were peeled off from *Shatavari* root .
4. Then *Kwath* of *Shatavari* root was prepared by adding 8 liter water in it.
5. After that *Shatavari Kwath* was prepared by reducing it 1/8th part i.e.1 liter and filtered through muslin cloth.

Precautions :

1. *Mandagni* should be maintained throughout the whole procedure.
2. Continuous stirring should be done to avoid spillage out during boiling of *Shatavari Kwath*.

Images showing ingredients of *Shatavari Kalpa* preparation :

Shatavari Mool

Khanda Sharkara

Sariva

Ela

Images showing preparation of *Shatavari Kwath* preparation :

Addition of water

Soaked *Shatavari*

Peeled off *Shatavari*

Kwath preparation

Addition of *Shatavari*

B. Preparation of *Shatavari Kalpa* :

1. 1 liter *Shatavari Kwath* was divided into two batches containing 500 ml *Kwath* in each batch.
2. Then *Samabhag Sharkara* that of *Shatavari Kwath* i.e 500 gm *Sharkara* was added in batch A and *Dwibhag Sharkara* that of *Shatavari Kwath* i.e 1 Kg *Sharkara* was added in batch B.
3. Then it was subjected to *Mandagni* and *Phenodgam* was observed after adding *Sharkara* to *Kwath*.
4. Continuous stirring was done during whole procedure and temperature was maintained between 90-100 °C till attained the *Rawa Halwa* like consistency.
5. At this stage whole mixture was removed from *Agni* and after some time fine powderd of *Prakshep Dravya Sariva* and *Ela* was added.
6. Then *Shatavari Kalpa* was packed in air tight container.
7. Same procedure was done for batch B .

Precautions :

1. *Shatavari* root should be washed properly before using.
2. *Nal* should be peeled off from *Shatavari* roots.
3. Continuous stirring should be done during whole procedure.
4. Temperature should be maintained between 90-100 °C .

Images showing preparation of *Shatavari Kalpa* preparation :

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS:

1) *Phenodgma* was observed during

Shatavari Kalpa
Shatavari Kwath.

Addition of *Kalpa*

Shatavari granules

Rawa Halwa like consistency

- 2) After adding *Sharkara* (Sugar) to the *Kwath*, effervescence was observed, which subsided on constant stirring.
- 3) Gradual thickening of syrup, consistency of *Tantumtwa* (threadlike) and *Darvi Pralepa* (adhesion of syrup to spoon), was observed in 30 min of heating.
- 4) After 40 min of heating, the syrup was found to be in two thread consistency with *Apsumajjan* (Dipping in water). *Bindu Paka* (Settled drop of syrup in water) with *Patitastu Na Shiriyate* (not instant dissolution in water) was observed after 50 min.
- 5) *Shatavari Kalpa* was obtained in two batches.

Table no 2. showing temperature record during preparation of *Shatavari Kwath*

Sr.no.	Temperature in °C	Observations
1	23	<i>Kwath</i> started
2	55	<i>Phenodgam</i> started
3	75	<i>Phenodgam</i> continued
4	80	Boiling started
5	84	Boiling continued
6	90	Boiling continued
7	90	Boiling continued
8	95	<i>Kwath</i> prepared

Table no 3. showing observation of Batch A

Sr.no.	Temperature in °C	Observation
1	53	Sugar added in <i>Shatavari Kwath</i>
2	70	Sugar completely melted , <i>Phenodgam</i>
3	75	Gradual thickening of <i>Kwath, Darvi Pralep</i>
4	87	<i>Bindu Paka</i>
5	98	<i>Halwa</i> like consistency <i>Agni</i> stopped.
6	-	Addition of <i>Prakshep Dravya</i>

Table no 4. showing observation of Batch B

Sr.no.	Temperature in °C	Observation
1	53	Sugar added in <i>Shatavari Kwath</i>
2	70	Sugar completely melted , <i>Phenodgam</i>
3	73	Gradual thickening of <i>Kwath, Darvi Pralep</i>
4	87	<i>Bindu Paka</i>
5	95	<i>Halwa</i> like consistency <i>Agni</i> stopped.
6	-	Addition of <i>Prakshep Dravya</i>

Table no 5. showing organoleptic character of *Shatavari Kalpa* Batch A&B

Sr . No	Parameter	Observation
1	Color	Creamish
2	Odor	-
3	Taste	<i>Madhur , Tikta</i>

Quantitative analysis during preparation of *Shatavari Kalpa*

Batch	Quantity of <i>Shatavari Kwath</i>	Quantity of <i>Sharkara</i>	Quantity obtained of <i>Shatavari Kalpa</i>	Duration
Batch A	500 ml	500 gm	512 gm	5 hrs
Batch B	500 ml	1 Kg	975 gm	4.40 hrs

Uses of *Shatavari Kalpa*:

- ✓ *Rasayan*
- ✓ *Vrushya*
- ✓ *Garbhaposhak*
- ✓ *Balya*
- ✓ *Stanyajanan*
- ✓ *Hrudya*
- ✓ *Grahi*
- ✓ *Amlapittahar*
- ✓ *Mutral*

Mode of Action :

- The guru and *Snigdha Guna* of *Shtatavari* works well against *Vata* and beneficial for *Vata-Pitta* disorders.
- *Vata Dosha* is responsible for all types of *Yonivyapad*(gynecological disorders) and *Artav Dushti* hence it is effective on *Yonirogas*.
- Due to its *Madhur Rasa*, *Shatavari* is known to be *Garbhasthapak* (Maintains pregnancy), useful in the prevention of abortions.

DISCUSSION:

1. Excessive frothing was observed during preparation of *Kwath* and after adding Sugar to *Kwath* due to Saponin which is constituent of *Shatavari* roots.
2. As the moisture content reduces in syrup cohesive force increases and further application of heat imparts kinetic movement to the Sugar molecules, where as when it is cooled loss of kinetic movement makes the Sugar molecules to coalesce. This explains the reasoning behind thickening and solidifying on cooling.^[6]
3. Temperature during whole process was maintained under 100 °C for optimum preservation of active constituents in the product.
4. *Prakshep Dravya* was added to make it more palatable.

CONCLUSION :

The adopted manufacturing procedure can be accepted as SMP (standard manufacturing procedure) for *Shatavari Kalpa*. 512 gm granules were prepared from *Samabhag Sharkara* and . 975 gm granules were prepared from *Dwibhag Sharkara* in average 5.30 hrs at 90-100 °C continuously maintained temperature. As standards for granules are not mentioned in API, hence present study can be considered for future research.

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